

Sequence of monomers and position of stereocenters matter for thermal properties of stereocontrolled oligourethanes.

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Abstract:

Polyurethanes are commodity materials used for multiple applications. In recent years, a new category of polyurethane material has emerged, characterized by the lack of polymer molar mass distribution, control of the monomer arrangement in the chain, and even full stereocontrol. Various multistep synthesis strategies have been developed to fabricate sequence-defined polyurethanes. However, synthesizing stereocontrolled polyurethanes with a controlled sequence is still a challenge. Polyurethanes with structural precision, as represented by biopolymers, i.e. proteins or nucleic acids, have opened new application directions for these groups of materials. It has been shown that polyurethanes can be used as biomimetics, information carriers, molecular tags, and materials with strictly controlled properties. Precise synthesis of macromolecules allows us to fine-tune the properties of polymers to specific needs. Therefore, it is essential to collect information on the sequence-structure relationship of polymers. In our work, we present synthetic pathways to make sequence and stereo-defined oligourethanes. We demonstrate that structural details, i.e., the monomer sequences and position of the stereocenter, have a tremendous effect on the thermal properties of model oligourethanes. We show that the introduction of chirality by constitutional isomerization can be used to program the thermal characteristics of polymers, which are key features for material applications.

Introduction

Polyurethanes are remarkably adaptable materials widely exploited in various domains including foams, coatings, adhesives, sealants, and elastomers.[1] The global polyurethane market size was estimated at 80 billion USD in 2022 and is projected to increase thanks to favorable mechanical properties surpassing alternative materials.[2] These data pertain to classical polyurethanes utilized as commodities. Nowadays, polyurethanes can be fabricated as discrete macromolecules with defined monomer order and controlled stereochemistry.[3–5] Synthetic polyurethanes with defined monomer sequences serve as a versatile structural platform that can be explored by incorporating different monomer types, leading to diverse structures, properties, applications, and functionalities. For example, sequence-defined polyurethanes have been used as biomimetics,[6–11] materials for data storage,[12–14] or molecular tags[15–18]. However, manipulation of monomer sequence in polyurethanes remains largely unexplored in applied domains. The reason is challenging synthesis protocol for their large-scale fabrication.

Recently, significant progress has been made in the realm of polymer chemistry, leading to the development of techniques for the synthesis of sequence and stereo-defined polymers.[19–21] Typically, these methodologies rely on iterative synthesis processes, which can be conducted either on the solid phase[12,22] or in solution.[3,4,18,23] While purification steps during solid-phase synthesis are simplified due to the use of a polymer resin support, it demands higher reagent excesses to overcome hindrances of coupling reactions. However, this approach faces practical limitations including the cost of solid support, reagent wastage, and solvent consumption. Therefore, solution-phase synthesis emerges as a more attractive method. This is due to its potential to achieve higher yields and overcome the drawbacks associated with purification steps. In our previous studies, we significantly optimized the oligourethane solution synthesis protocol by strategically reducing the frequency of purification steps. Initially, purification was conducted after each synthesis step,[18,23] but through our optimization efforts, we limited to isolation solely after coupling.[3] Subsequently, we further advanced the methodology by implementing a one-pot approach, isolating the product after the final coupling.[4] These innovative approaches not only enhance the efficiency of the synthesis process but also enable the production of short oligomers on a large scale, resulting in substantial improvements in yield while maintaining a high level of purity. Despite these advancements, further optimization is necessary to yield longer polyurethane characterized by sequence and stereocontrol.

The thermal properties of polymer materials serve as critical indicators of their characteristics. According to thermal characteristics, polymers are classified as thermoplastics, duroplasts and rubbery materials that guide their future applications.[24,25] Key parameters include the glass transition temperature (T_g), indicative of the amorphous region of the polymer, and the melting point (T_m), characterizing its crystalline area. Another parameter frequently determined during the analysis of thermal polymer properties is the thermal degradation temperature (T_d) calculated from a thermogravimetric curve. Besides chemical composition, these parameters can be adjusted by discrete structural changes, e.g., monomer sequence [26–28] and stereocontrol preserving chemical formula and functional groups. It was reported that the thermal characteristics of discrete polymers are affected by their stereoconfiguration, though the trend of these changes is not completely understood and clear. In the case of stereocontrolled polymers the chain length,[29,30] number of chiral centers,[3] and order of chiral monomers[3,31] matters. Typically, the melting and glass transition temperatures increase with regularity in the sequence of stereocenters. [31–33] However, the effect of stereocenter position has not been investigated so far. A deeper understanding of the relationship between monomer sequence and properties is necessary to improve engineering of polymer materials.

In this work, we investigated the thermal properties of model, stereocontrolled, sequence-defined oligourethanes. We demonstrated a synthetic strategy to fabricate 8-mer long oligomers with control of stereochemistry and sequence by scalable solution-phase approach. We examined how the introduction of the chiral center, and its position influences the thermal properties of the studied library of model oligomers. We demonstrated that thermal characteristics are susceptible to discrete structural changes. Data can be used to guide the programming of polyurethanes with desired material properties.

Results and Discussion

Library of sequence-defined and stereocontrolled oligomers was prepared by the multistep synthesis in solution (Fig. 1). We applied an iterative cycle of two reactions: activation of alcohol group with *N,N*-disuccinimidyl carbonate (i) and chemoselective coupling of amino alcohol (ii) in one pot, as described previously.[3] To reduce the number of synthesis steps, tetramers obtained by the multistep approach were deprotected and used as macromonomers to fabricate 8-mer-long oligourethanes with an average yield >60% (Table S2). For synthesis, we used aminopropanol (A) and three chiral monomer building blocks based on an aminoethanol skeleton with methyl substituents at carbon adjacent to the amine (BS), methyl at carbon adjacent to the oxygen (CS) and benzyl (PS). A prepared set of oligomers enables the systematic study to look up how structural details, e.g., the presence of stereocenters, the position of stereocenters, type of substituent, and sequence, influence oligomer thermal characteristics. Studied oligomers are listed in Table 1.

Figure 1. The general procedure of solution-phase, stepwise synthesis of sequence-defined oligourethanes is as follows: the synthesis involves repetitive cycles of three steps: activation of alcohol group with *N,N*-disuccinimidyl carbonate (i), chemoselective coupling of amino alcohol (ii), and *N*-hydroxysuccinimide waste removal by water wash (iii). Part of the formed tetramers were deprotected and coupled with Boc-protected tetramer to yield octamers.

Structures of obtained oligourethanes were confirmed by liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (LC-MS, Fig. S2-S9), gel permeation chromatography (GPC, Fig. S10-S17), and ¹H NMR (Fig. S18-S25) analyses. In LC-MS chromatogram (UV, 220 nm) for all studied samples, we observe a single signal with *m/z* corresponding to [M+H]⁺, [M+Na]⁺, and formed by spontaneous fragmentation [M-Boc+2H]²⁺ ions. Calculated monoisotopic mass and experimentally determined *m/z* are collected in Table 1. Oligomers OU3-OU8 have equal

molar masses but different content and positions of stereocenters and various sequences (alternated and alternated dyads). GPC analyses of crude products present monomodal molar mass distribution (Fig. S10-S17). Observed signals characterized by slight differences in elution time depending on oligomer composition (Fig. 2B). In the ^1H NMR spectra, all signals originating from the proton groups respective to the analyzed molecules were detected and attributed, thereby confirming the chemical structure of the oligomers. Fig. 2A presents representative spectra for 3 oligomers, OU4, OU6, and OU8, with the same molar mass but built from various aliphatic monomers. Signals from Boc (1.40 ppm), methyl (0.9-1.2 ppm), backbone protons (N-CH₂- at 4.0-4.5 ppm, O-CH₂- at 3.0-3.5 ppm, -CH₂- at 1.5-1.8 ppm), -CH₂- from benzyl side chain (2.5-3.0 ppm), urethane amines (4.6-6.75 ppm), and aromatics (7.0-7.3 ppm) occur in a specific ppm range. A specific pattern of proton signal characterizes each sequence depending on the sequence, composition, and position of stereocenters (Fig. S18-S25). For example, comparing oligomers OU6 and OU8, we observe that the signal from the methyl substituent relative to the position is characterized by a different shape (Fig. 2A), indicating a diverse chemical environment, which is a consequence of various spatial rearrangements of substituent.

Table 1. Library of investigated oligourethanes.

Oligomer	Sequence	$M_{\text{mi}}^{[\text{a}]}$ [g/mol]	$m/z^{[\text{b}]}$
OU1	Boc-P _S AAAAAAA	958.4859	959.4963
OU2	Boc-P _S AAAAAAP _S	1034.5172	1035.5262
OU3	Boc-P _S AP _S AP _S AP _S A	1186.5798	1187.5877
OU4	Boc-P _S P _S AAP _S P _S AA	1186.5798	1187.5907
OU5	Boc-P _S B _S P _S B _S P _S B _S P _S B _S	1186.5798	1187.5861
OU6	Boc-P _S P _S B _S B _S P _S P _S B _S B _S	1186.5798	1187.5880
OU7	Boc-P _S C _S P _S C _S P _S C _S P _S C _S	1186.5798	1187.5926
OU8	Boc-P _S P _S C _S C _S P _S P _S C _S C _S	1186.5798	1187.5868

[a] calculated monoisotopic mass; [b] m/z determined experimentally for $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$ ion form LC-MS analyses note.

Figure 2. (A) Structures of OU4, OU6, and OU8 oligomers built from various aliphatic monomers: achiral - A, chiral with a methyl substituent at carbon attached to nitrogen - B and chiral with a methyl substituent at carbon attached to oxygen – C. Structure of oligomers was confirmed by ¹H NMR analysis that shows proton signals are occurring in structure characteristic ppm ranges. (B) Representative GPC chromatograms of OU4, OU6 and OU8.

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) analyses revealed a substantial dependence between the number of stereocenters, stereocenter position, and the monomer sequence on the thermal properties of the analyzed oligourethanes. Although the analyzed macromolecules had the same molar mass (OU3-OU8) and chemical formula, the subtle changes in structure at the level of constitutional isomerization significantly impacted material properties. Based on DSC curve recorded during 2nd heating cycle of samples, a significant shift in T_g values was observed when aliphatic monomers A were replaced with chiral monomers Bs and Cs (Fig. 3). Substitution of 1-amino-3-propanol (monomer A, OU3, OU4) with its constitutional isomer 1-amino-1-propanol (monomer Bs, OU5, OU6) cause a notable increase in T_g values irrespectively from the sequence. In the case of alternated oligomers (OU3, OU5), T_g changes from 48.0°C to 58.2°C. For alternated dyads OU4 and OU6, the increase is much more

pronounced, leading to a change from 47.5°C to 64.3°C. In contrast, for the alternated sequence if 1-amino-2-propanol Cs substitutes monomer A, the Tg decreases to 39.0°C. The impact on Tg is strongly sequence-dependent because, for alternated dyads, Tg rises to 60.0°C. Comparing alternated and alternated dyads sequences, we do not observe changes in the case of sequences containing non-chiral monomer A (OU3, OU4). Yet, if oligomers are built from stereocontrolled building blocks, the sequence effect is tremendous. For OU5 and OU6, ΔT_g is 6.1°C, whereas for OU7 and OU8, ΔT_g equals 21°C. We speculate that this unexpected behavior can be guided by the secondary structure of oligomers that can strongly influence chain mobility and their packing in the material.

Figure 3. DSC curves (2nd heating) of alternated (OU3, OU5, OU7, A) and alternated diads (OU4, OU6, OU8, B) oligourethanes with marked enthalpy relaxation (ΔH). The Tg values were determined from the deflection point of the DSC curve (2nd heating).[34,35]

An increase in the content of aromatic monomers causes a notable effect on Tg. Traditional polyurethanes are built from soft and rigid segments. Therefore, they exhibit attractive properties for many applications. Soft elements usually are flexible oligomeric aliphatic or

ether segments, whereas rigid parts are formed by aromatic compounds. The ratio and size of those segments are commonly used to tune material thermal properties.[36,37] In general, increasing the proportion of stiff aromatic segments shifts the Tg towards high values. Here, we compared the DCS curves of 4 oligomers with 1, 2, 4 (OU1-OU4) aromatic monomers (Fig. 4), and we observed that by increasing the content of aromatic units, we could alter Tg values of about 20°C irrespectively to sequence. A similar ΔT_g effect can be achieved by changing the sequence of oligomers built from stereocontrolled blocks (OU7, OU8), preserving chemical composition. This observation suggests that chirality and chain conformation play significant roles in material characteristics.

Figure 4. DSC curves (2nd heating) of oligourethanes build from non-chiral 1-amino-3-propanol and aromatic monomers (OU1-OU4) with marked enthalpy relaxation (ΔH). The Tg values were determined from the deflection point of the DSC curve (2nd heating).[34,35]

The DSC data revealed that an enthalpy relaxation (ΔH) signal accompanies observed glass transitions. The relaxation enthalpy corresponds to the release of degrees of freedom upon heating as an effect of material ageing below its glass transition temperature.[38] It is a phenomenon indicating that these materials are in a non-equilibrium state when maintained at temperatures below their Tg. Here, we used a 10 K/minute cooling rate up to -50 °C in the analysis conditions. Materials allowed cooling slowly exhibit the least excess enthalpy, as their polymer chains have time to find energetically advantageous orientations. They are closer to thermodynamic equilibrium than those cooled rapidly, where, polymer chains are captured into high-energy conformations. In particular, significant enthalpy relaxation occurs for oligomers OU3 and OU5. The increase in relaxation enthalpy values indicates the ordering of chains in the materials and the tendency to achieve higher thermodynamic stability at a given

temperature. Based on obtained DSC curves, we speculate that each oligomer represents a characteristic tendency to form order structure in materials depending on composition, sequence and position of chiral center, as each compound shows various amplitudes of the relaxation enthalpy.

Crystallinity and melting temperature are another key characteristic of polyurethane materials. Among analyzed samples, we observed a melting signal only for three of the tested oligomers (OU1, OU3, OU7) looking at the DSC curve (visible during 1st heating) (Fig. S26, Table 2). The exothermic signal characteristic for the crystalline phase was observed upon second heating only for OU7 oligomer (Fig. S28). In order to determine T_m values we used van Krevelen theoretical method (Table 2).[39] The van Krevelen additive groups theory is based on a function Y_m , characterized by dimensions of $K \cdot kg \cdot mol^{-1}$ (Table S3). The increments for this function have been derived from a comprehensive review of literature data encompassing nearly 800 crystalline melting points of polymers. However, it's important to note that Y_m , doesn't exhibit simple linear additivity due to intricate intra- and inter-molecular interactions between structural groups. Although many of the groups' contributions and their structural corrections are available for calculation, it is important to approach this data methodically, keeping in mind that the model does not account for differences in monomer sequences concerning isomers. In our examination of the theoretical melting points of oligourethanes, intriguing patterns have emerged. Specifically, we have observed that sequences incorporating chiral segments instead of monomer A exhibit higher melting temperatures (T_m) compared to their achiral counterparts, as evidenced by the differences between OU5-OU8 and OU3-OU4. These theoretical findings align with our previous report on sequence-defined tetramers.[3] This consistency further underscores the significance of chiral elements in influencing the thermal properties of oligourethanes, providing valuable insights into the factors governing their crystallinity and melting behavior. However, it is notable that the oligomer comprised predominantly of achiral, aliphatic A monomers (OU1, OU2) exhibits exceptionally high T_m values. If we refer to the results obtained from experiments for OU1, OU3 and OU7, it demonstrates that this observation does not align with the expected outcomes - the most achiral oligomer exhibits a lower T_m compared to OU3 and OU7. This discrepancy highlights the limitations of the theoretical model in fully explaining the observed thermal properties of oligourethanes. However, despite this inconsistency, a discernible trend towards increased crystallinity remains evident. As a result, the model's inability to capture changes in melting temperatures resulting from monomer sequences limits its reliability to some extent. As other

thermal properties of our oligourethane library have shown, the sequence plays a significant role in the properties of oligomers. Thus, although additive group theory provides valuable insights, it must be interpreted with caution given the complexity introduced by monomer sequences.

Table 2. Thermal properties of oligourethanes.

Sequence	T _g [°C] ^a	T _m [°C] ^b	T _{m calc} [°C] ^c	T _{d, 5%} [°C] ^d	T _{max} [°C] ^e	wt% ^f
Boc-P ₅ AAAAAAA OU1	25.2	106.3	311.9	231.8	266.5	7.01
Boc-P ₅ AAAAAAP ₅ OU2	25.3	-	362.5	205.5	287.2	1.84
Boc-P ₅ AP ₅ AP ₅ AP ₅ A OU3	48	141.3	290.8	230.8	260.8	1.69
Boc-P ₅ P ₅ AAP ₅ P ₅ AA OU4	47.5	-	290.8	226.8	264.2	1.51
Boc-P ₅ B ₅ P ₅ B ₅ P ₅ B ₅ P ₅ B ₅ OU5	58.2	-	296.3	234.2	262.2	1.14
Boc-P ₅ P ₅ B ₅ B ₅ P ₅ P ₅ B ₅ B ₅ OU6	64.3	-	296.3	231.2	239.5	0.94
Boc-P ₅ C ₅ P ₅ C ₅ P ₅ C ₅ P ₅ C ₅ OU7	39	199.2	296.3	238.8	261	0.31
Boc-P ₅ P ₅ C ₅ C ₅ P ₅ P ₅ C ₅ C ₅ OU8	60	-	296.3	228.8	245	0.35

[a] Glass transition temperature calculated in deflection point of DSC curve (2nd heating). [b] Melting temperature calculated as a minimum from DSC curve (1st heating), under these experimental conditions (10 K/min), melting peaks were not observed for oligomers OU2, OU4-OU6, OU8. [c] T_m calculated by van Krevelen theoretical method. [d] Decomposition temperature at 5% weight loss read from TGA curve. [e] Degradation temperature determined at a maximum of the dTGA curve. [f] Percentage weight of residues after degradation.

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) of sequence-defined oligourethanes with stereocontrol has revealed a notable influence of sequence and composition on their thermal stability. Typically, the onset of thermal decomposition for polyurethanes is observed around 200°C being contingent upon the monomers employed in their synthesis.[35,36,40] It has been observed that both the composition of monomers within the chain and the functional groups incorporated therein significantly affect the degradation temperature. The degradation process of polyurethanes typically proceeds in two distinct stages due to the coexistence of hard and soft segments. Conducted TGA analysis of the oligourethanes shows that degradation occurs at temperatures exceeding 200°C (Fig. 5). Notably, each oligomer exhibits a diverse TGA curve with characteristic dTGA pattern. The dissimilarities observed in the degradation temperatures of the oligomers may indicate the prevalence of distinct degradation mechanisms involved in each sequence. Generally, oligourethanes consisting of chiral monomers exhibit slightly higher thermal stability compared to those constructed from non-chiral units A. Detailed information

regarding the precise decomposition temperatures and residual weights subsequent to degradation is provided in Table 2. It is observed that the composition of oligourethane has the most influential effect on their degradation. The T_d , 5% ranges from 205°C to 238°C depending on used building blocks. Regarding monomer sequence, the difference can reach up to ΔT_d , 5%=10°C. Interestingly, we also observed that the sequence of monomers for oligomers of the same composition has an impact on the degradation pathway. For instance, dTGA curves for alternated oligomers OU5 and OU7 have two maxima, whereas respective alternated dyads OU6 and OU8 have three maxima, indicating alterations in the degradation process (Fig. 5). This difference is not caused by the chemical nature of the oligomers, as they are made of identical elements. Hence, the reasons for these differences may be found in their conformation differences and chain packing.

Figure 5. Comparison of TGA thermograms and dTGA curves of the different sets of oligourethanes to visualize the effect of incorporation of aromatic segment, sequence, and position of chiral center.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the protocol presented herein for multistep synthesis offers a practical means of generating stereocontrolled, sequence-defined oligourethanes. Using oligomeric precursors reduces number of synthesis steps. In principle, the process is amenable to scaling up as all steps are conducted in the solution phase. The precise modulation of thermal properties in polyurethanes is achieved through the sensible selection and arrangement of specific monomer building blocks in the chain. Incorporating chiral or aromatic monomers enables fine-tuning of glass transition temperatures, with chiral units exerting an as pronounced effect on T_g as aromatic counterparts. We showed that the position of the stereocenter in the backbone matters and causes significant alterations in T_g values. Most examples demonstrate that introducing aromatic or aliphatic chiral monomers notably enhances T_g values by constraining molecular motions and conformations within stereocontrolled structures. However, some exceptions display the opposite behavior. Therefore, analyzing T_g and T_m of stereocontrolled polymers, we should also consider their tendency to fold or aggregate, which could deliver information to predict complex properties. Glass transition showed substantial sensitivity to monomer sequences that emerge as parameters to tune properties of polyurethanes preserving polymer composition. The sequence effect is most visible for oligomers composed fully of chiral monomers. The thermal degradation behavior is intricately linked to the composition and sequence of monomers within the macromolecular structure, thereby dictating the resultant degradation mechanism. By exploring synthetic tools to control monomer sequence and stereochemistry, we can engineer materials with meticulously programmed thermal properties, underscoring the utility of this approach in material design and complex system engineering.

Supporting Information

The supporting information includes LC-MS data, GPC chromatograms, NMR spectra, DSC thermograms, and a detailed description of the materials, methods, and experimental procedures.

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